

THE CROP DIVERSITY INDEX ANALYSIS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The main objective of the study is to analyze the degree and extent of crop diversification among farmers while utilizing econometric models. We calculated the diversification index based on the Simpson diversity index method. The study revealed that the mean computed Simpson Index values indicate that the diversity index was found to be 0.59, 0.45, 0.56 and 0.62 for the Andijan, Karakalpakstan, Kashkadarya and Tashkent regions, respectively. This suggests that the farmers in the study areas were not too diversified in their cropping pattern. Cultivating several crop species also helps the farmers manage both price and production risks, which provides more food options for the household and income through marketing the produce from surpluses.*

Keywords: *Crop diversification, Simpson diversification index, cropping patterns, Uzbekistan.*

Аннотация. *Ушбу тадқиқот ишининг асосий мақсади фермер хўжаликлари миқёсида экинларни диверсификация қилишининг наъмунаси ва даражасини аниқлашдан иборат. Бунда биз диверсификация индексини Симпсон диверсификация индекси усулидан фойдаланган ҳолда амалга оширдик. Симпсон индекси орқали олинган натижаларга кўра ўртача диверсификация индекси кўрсаткичлари мос равишда Андижон, Қорақалпоғистон, Қашқадарё ва Тошкент вилоятлари учун 0.59, 0.45, 0.56 ва 0.62 ларни ташиқил этди. Бу шуни кўрсатадики, ўрганилган ҳудудлардаги фермер хўжаликлари экин майдонлари кўп ҳам диверсификациялашган бўлмаган. Экинлар хилма-хиллигини ошириш фермер хўжаликларига турли нарх ва ишлаб чиқариш хавфларини бошқариш ҳамда уй хўжаликлари учун озиқ-овқат хавфсизлигини таъминлашга ҳамда даромадларни янада оширишга ёрдам беради.*

Таянч сўзлар: *Экинлар диверсификацияси, Симпсон диверсификация индекси, экинлар наъмуналари, Ўзбекистон.*

Аннотация. *Основная цель исследования - проанализировать степень и степень диверсификации сельскохозяйственных культур среди фермеров. Мы рассчитали индекс диверсификации на основе метода индекса разнообразия Симпсона. Исследование показало, что средние рассчитанные значения индекса Симпсона указывают на то, что индекс разнообразия был найден 0.59, 0.45, 0.56 и 0.62 для Андижанской, Каракалпакской, Кашкадарьинской и Ташкентской областей соответственно. Это говорит о том, что фермеры в исследуемых районах не были слишком разнообразны в своей структуре посевов. Выращивание нескольких видов сельскохозяйственных культур также помогает фермерам управлять как ценовыми, так и производственными рисками, что позволяет получить больше вариантов продуктов питания для семьи и доходов за счет сбыта продукции из излишков.*

Ключевые слова: *Диверсификация сельскохозяйственных культур, индекс диверсификации Симпсона, модели посевов, Узбекистан.*

Introduction The agriculture sector plays a highly important role in Uzbekistan’s overall economy. For two and a half decades, the production of higher value crops, such as fruit and vegetables, was constrained by limited access to land, inputs, modern crop-specific technologies, and finance and agricultural policies were more highlighted at the strategically significant crops cotton and winter wheat [2]. Following independence, the country has managed to gradually move away from cotton monoculture towards a more diversified pattern of agricultural produce, including cereals, potatoes, vegetables and melons [4]. Therefore, the national administration has recently issued crucial legislative policies to enhance crop diversification throughout the country [5]. Karimov (2013) indicated that enhancing crop productivity at the farm level plays an essential role in developing economic growth, improving food security, and easing poverty in the country. The government ought to carry on crop diversification among farmers, as it supports obtaining extra income, improves food security, and lessens famine [4]. Bobojonov (2013) also indicated that diversification is explained as the addition of more crops into the existing cropping system, increases farm income, and minimizes risk management practices on the farm level. Crop diversification is an effective strategy to deal with problems such as water scarcity, drought, and salinity. The land is available for high-value alternative crops. However, the cultivation of these types of crops is very limited despite their high economic and ecological potential [3]. Moreover, comprehensive studies of crop diversification in Uzbekistan are still sparse, and most studies are based on statistical data results; only limited research on this subject has been conducted in Uzbekistan to date [3]. To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no study to date that has attempted to provide an additional, comprehensive understanding of the status and extent of crop diversification of the farmers at the farm level in different parts (regions) of Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods. This study chose to analyze the four regions of Uzbekistan: The Republic of Karakalpakstan, Kashkadaryo, Tashkent, and Andijan because these provinces are in different parts of the country.

Four districts (Karakalpakstan, Kashkadaryo, Tashkent, and Andijan) from Uzbekistan were included in gathering this data. The four districts were purposively selected in terms of agroecological, crop production, and marketing access. Tashkent and Andijan provinces have great potential in both cases; however, Karakalpakstan and Kashkadarya districts are in low-potential zones, respectively. The Simpson Diversity Index was measured while utilizing Stata version 14 statistical software tools to measure the extent of the crop diversification index for the crops of interest in the study areas.

The extent of crop diversification can be measured by using several indices Simpson’s Index (SI), Composite Entropy Index (CEI), and Shannon Index (ShI). In terms of data availability and crop patterns, this study employed the Simpson Diversity Index (SDI) because it is the most used index in numerous studies related to crop diversification [1, 2]. The Simpson Index (SID) is calculated using the following equation:

$$SID = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i^2 \quad (1)$$

where, A_i is the value or area of the i^{th} commodities and P_i is the proportionate value or area of the i^{th} commodities in the total value or area. The index ranges between 0 and 1 value. If the values are close to 1 point at a more diversified cropping pattern or complete diversification, a value of 0 indicates, in contrast, a situation of monoculture or complete specialization.

Table 1. Category of crop diversification based on value

Category	SID value
No diversification	≤ 0.01
Low level diversification	0.01 to 0.25
Medium level diversification	0.26 to 0.50
High level diversification	0.51 to 0.75
Very high-level diversification	> 0.75

Result and discussion. Farmers have cultivated around 23 crops, including cereals, pulses, root vegetables, and tubers, by dividing the cropping season into four distinct periods. The average Crop Diversification Index (CDI) among the sampled farmers was 0.56, with a standard deviation of 0.17. Most farmers exhibited a high level of diversification intensity in different parts of Uzbekistan (Table 2). However, approximately 11% of farmers have not engaged in any form of crop diversification or cultivated only one or two crops as per state orders.

Table 2. Level of crop diversification of farmers

Category	SID value	Number of respondents	Percentage
No diversification	≤ 0.01	43	10.91
Low level diversification	0.01 to 0.25	32	8.12
Medium level diversification	0.26 to 0.50	125	31.73
High level diversification	0.51 to 0.75	184	46.70
Very high-level diversification	> 0.75	10	2.54

The finding was almost comparable with Bobojonov et al. (2013), who found 0.65 in Khorezm. Figure 3 also presents the regional and district levels of crop diversification. Table 1 shows that the mean Simpson Index was 0.59, 0.45, 0.56, and 0.62 for Andijan, Karakalpakstan, Kashkadarya, and Tashkent states, respectively.

Figure 1. Regional and district level of crop diversification in study areas

This shows that Tashkent region farmers shifted towards more diverse cropping patterns than their counterparts in the country. In addition, the overall result in the four states combined in this study reveals a mean Simpson Index within the sample of farmers of 0.56. This implies that the farmers in the study areas were not too diversified in their cropping patterns.

Conclusion. Crop diversification is considered a key potential strategy for improving inclusive farm income and household food security. The study has examined the degree and extent of crop diversification at the farm level across different states of Uzbekistan. The Simpson Index values indicate that the mean computed diversity index was found to be 0.59, 0.45, 0.56 and 0.62 for the Andijan, Karakalpakstan, Kashkadarya and Tashkent regions, respectively. This implies that the Tashkent region farmers shifted towards more diverse cropping patterns than their country counterparts. We therefore conclude that crop diversification enhances the availability of foods for households and the income of farmers.

Cultivating several crop species helps the farmers manage both price and production risks, which provides more food options for the household and income through marketing the produce from surpluses. Therefore, the government needs to intensify the promotion of crop diversification to increase farm income and food security in the country.

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